

QUIET DRONES
International Symposium
on
UAV/UAS Noise
Remote from Paris – 19th to 21st October 2020

**Two Dimensional Convolutional Neural Network Frameworks
Using Acoustic Nodes for UAV Security Applications**

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Abstract

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have become increasingly popular to the public with a multitude of associated applications in real life. However, malicious applications of UAVs, such as terrorism and air transport disturbance may occur with devastating consequences. Therefore, counter-UAV (C-UAV) systems are required to efficiently address these undesired situations. Artificial intelligence approaches, such as deep neural networks (DNNs), are deemed crucial for high accuracy detection and real-time response of the next generation C-UAV systems. UAV detection based on acoustic sensors has received a great research interest over the past years, however the performance of the proposed solutions may vary in different

environments, since sound signals from UAVs are multi-source and unstructured. In this work, three different 2D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) using short-time Fourier transform spectrograms as input, for UAV binary classification in real-world settings, are compared. The results confirm that 2D CNNs, along with data augmentation techniques in the image domain, can capture the spatio-temporal information of the UAV sound signals, even in noisy environments, and obtain a 95.35% macro average F1-Score in a dataset collected from two different environments.

1. Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) or Systems (UASs) are becoming a part of citizens' everyday life. UAVs bring a continuous market increase in a growing number of useful applications such as construction [1], agriculture [2], insurance [3] and internet communications [4]. However the rapid spread of UAVs is generating serious security issues. In recent years, newspapers and mass media have reported dozens of incidents involving drones flying over restricted areas and around critical infrastructures or during public events. On December 2018, a UAV was spotted flying close to Gatwick airport ultimately causing the closure of Britain's second largest airport for 36 h and disrupting 1000 flights [5]. Moreover, in September 2013, Chancellor Merkel has been threatened by a Parrot AR Drone which landed at her feet without any reaction from her security service. It turned out that the drone was sent by the Pirate Party, in an attempt to raise her awareness about drones' dangerous potential [6]. As a consequence, it has become important to develop effective and affordable countermeasures to report of a drone flying over critical areas.

Various types of sensors such as thermal [7], electro-optical [8] and radar [9] have been proposed in the literature for the data acquisition in the UAV detection field. However, C-UAV systems consisted of the above sensors may contain some drawbacks. First, although thermal sensors are excellent for night-time surveillance, they face issues with humidity and other adverse environmental settings [10]. Moreover, electro-optical sensors are able to detect the target when it is visible but the occlusions, night-time and low visibility affect their performance [11]. Finally, radar is invariant to environmental settings but may lack in classification capabilities. On the other hand, acoustic sensors overcome these drawbacks using a low cost infrastructure as well. Acoustic sensors are robust to environmental settings and provide adequate classification capabilities which make them a reliable choice [12] [13].

In this paper an audio-based UAV binary classification approach in real-world settings is proposed. The main contributions are summarized as follows:

- A large drone flight dataset was collected under a variety of conditions. Various types of drones were recorded in two different environments under diverse weather conditions and background noises.
- An end-to-end procedure was implemented since the model was trained on features learnt by the DNN in contrast to computationally intensive hand-crafted ones.
- Three different deep learning architectures were compared achieving high classification performances. Their results were evaluated and each one's limitations and applications were analyzed.

2. Related Work

Over the last few years, many researchers have worked on acoustic scene classification, by recognizing single events in monophonic recordings [14]. Different feature extraction techniques [15] and data augmentation [16] have been explored. Jeon et al. [17] showed that the classification performance increased when using data augmentation methods. The ability of DNNs to extract unique features from raw data and the high processing speeds of modern Graphic Processing Units (GPUs) lead these networks to receive a lot of attention in audio classification field. Particularly, CNNs have been applied and compared with other deep

learning architectures [18], resulting in better performance and making them the dominant methodology option.

In the field of audio-based detection of UAVs many different approaches have been proposed. Liu et al. [19] used the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), commonly used in the field of speech recognition, and a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier to detect UAVs. Recently, Kim et al. [20] introduced a real-time drone detection and monitoring system, using one microphone. This system used the k-nearest neighbors and plotted image learning algorithms to learn from properties of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) spectra. The authors extended their work [21] and increased the classification accuracy of their proposed system from 83% to 86%, using an artificial neural network. In all circumstances, there was a strong need for the collection of a real world UAV audio dataset and application of methods that overcome the noise sensitivity and the functionality in a confined dataset only.

3. Methodology

In this Section the methodology followed for a binary classification problem based on UAV's audio data is presented. According to Figure 1, after data annotation, the first step relies on audio-pre-processing which consists of trimming, resampling, adding silence as well as data augmentation techniques. Afterwards, a feature extraction procedure is implemented including the audio transformation to short-time Fourier spectrograms. The following phases include the training of three different CNNs as well as their performance evaluation based on precision, recall and F1-score metrics.

Figure 1: A general view of the applied methodology.

3.1 Audio data description

A critical issue in the UAV detection applications is the limited number of the public available datasets, both in number and size [22]. In this work, a large dataset was collected from two different environments under a variety of real-world conditions. During this investigation, various capturing sessions took place at the Markopoulo Training Facility, in Athens among 30/9/2019 – 4/10/2019. Furthermore, an additional dataset was recorded by Fraunhofer Institute for Digital Media Technology (IDMT), in Hude, Germany during the time period from 2017 to 2019. Both datasets were recorded by three eight-channel arrays with a sampling rate of 48 KHz and a 32-bit depth.

The dataset contained drone flights data in large areas. The flights altitudes ranged from 0 meters to 20 meters and the horizontal distances between a drone and the system, ranged from 1 meter to 200 meters. The final dataset contained 149982 seconds of monophonic audio data and was separated into two target classes, drones and false alarms (FA).

The annotation procedure was carried out manually by human annotators. In particular Information Technologies Institute of Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH), conducted the Markopoulo dataset annotation and Fraunhofer IDMT the one in Hude. The drone target class contained samples from different types of drones such as DJI Mavick, DJI Phantom 4, DJI Matrice 200, AAlign 470L, Sky hero Little Spyer, DJI F450, Parrot Disco (surfaceplane), Unique Taifun H520 – Hexacopter and some unknown drones. The aforementioned drone class included various drone flight scenarios such as drone in short and long distances, drone

with commercial aircraft background sound and drone with vehicles background sound. Accordingly, the false alarm class (not drone-class) included sound samples of animals, moving vehicles, wind noises and commercial aircrafts flights.

Figure 2: Audio waveform of (a) a drone class sample and (b) a false alarm class sample. The x-axis represents the time and the y-axis represents the amplitude of the sound.

3.2 Pre-process

One necessary step before the audio feature extraction procedure is the audio data pre-processing. Considering that the final system should operate in real-time, it was important to minimize the computational cost as much as possible. Therefore, the input signal was trimmed into smaller chunks of a constant interval. After several tests, three seconds of audio appeared to be sufficient for the network learning. Since some recordings had smaller duration than the appropriate one, an audio sample of silence was added in order to re-structure the collected information into a global form of data.

Furthermore, it was observed that the main energies of the drone frequencies reached up to approximately 8 kHz. Above that frequency, some harmonics had minimal energy in the frequency domain. Therefore, the information can be considered as insignificant for the network training. Hence, the 48 kHz recordings were down-sampled to 16 kHz and the computational cost was minimized.

To further increase the robustness of the network and avoid overfitting as much as possible, data augmentation techniques in the image domain were applied. Specifically, the height and width of the image were shifted randomly by 25% resulting in new, additional training data without changing the semantic meaning of the labels. Therefore, the performance of the CNN was enhanced and its ability of generalization was increased.

3.3 Feature Extraction

The feature extraction is an important step in pattern recognition systems. It transforms originally high-dimensional patterns into lower dimensional vectors by capturing the essence of their characteristics. Various feature extraction techniques have been proposed in the literature for environmental sound analysis. A few of them include Zero crossing rate [23], MFCCs [24], Mel band energy spectrograms [25] and Spectral centroids [26]. This work is focused on spectrogram based image features using the short-time Fourier Transform (STFT). Therefore, the two-dimensional CNN learns the spatio-temporal representation of the target classes.

After the 3-s audio trimming process and the 16 kHz resampling, the audio input signal was transformed in the time-frequency domain using STFT. For STFT, the discrete Fourier transform with a sliding Hanning window was applied to overlapping segments of the signal. Varying the window length, results in a trade-off between frequency and time resolution. By

using a window size of 512 samples and a hop length of 256, an equal significance was attributed on the aforementioned parameters.

Figure 3: Grayscale spectrogram images of (a) a drone and (b) a false alarm sample. The x-axis represents the time (s) and the y-axis the frequency (Hz). The colour represents the amplitude of a particular frequency with darker colours corresponding to low energies and bright colours corresponding to progressively higher energies.

Afterwards, the values were converted to a logarithmic scale (decibels) then normalized from [0, 255] to [0, 1], generating single-channel greyscale images (Figure 3). The dimensions of the aforementioned images were 257x188 pixels.

3.4 Network architecture

This work focused on the comparison of various two-dimensional CNN architectures under real world conditions. In particular, the Inception-V3 [27], Xception [28], and DenseNet-121[29] were applied in the context of this investigation in order to evaluate the impact of different architecture structures and sizes in UAV detection applications.

The initial annotated dataset consisted of 22,501 drones and 27,493 FA samples (Figure 4a). In the terms of the two-dimensional CNN learning, the aforementioned dataset was divided into training and validation set with a ratio of 70 (15,750 drones – 19,245 FA) and 30 (6,750 drones – 8,247 FA) percent respectively. Furthermore, the networks were tested on an unseen dataset, consisted of 1651 drones and 1309 FA samples (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Dataset distribution of (a) training and (b) test set for each class.

After the data pre-processing described in Section 3.2, the original and the augmented images were fed into the networks in batches of eight images per iteration. For this binary classification problem, the Adam [30] optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001 and the binary cross

entropy loss function for optimization were used. Moreover, the learning rate was reduced by a factor of 0.1 when there was no improvement after 5 epochs. The initial epoch number for the CNNs was 200 with an early stopping patience of 10 epochs.

4. Experimental results

In order to compare the deep learning architectures performance, the precision, recall and F1-Score for each class were calculated as well as their macro average scores (Table 1). According to Table 1, all experiments produced satisfactory results, since the capability of distinguishing very efficiently between drones and false alarm samples, is revealed. Particularly, Inception-V3, a 42-layer deep learning architecture, adding batch normalisation to the auxiliary layers results to a great classification performance. Nevertheless, the network size is large due to the high parameters count (24 million).

Table 1: Precision, recall and F1-Score metrics of the training set for each experiment.

Architecture		Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Inception-V3	Drones	99.34%	97.59%	98.45%
	False Alarms	98.05%	99.47%	98.75%
	Macro-avg	98.69%	98.53%	98.60%
Xception	Drones	99.37%	98.58%	98.97%
	False Alarms	98.84%	99.49%	99.17%
	Macro-avg	99.11%	99.03%	99.07%
DenseNet-121	Drones	97.81%	97.26%	97.53%
	False Alarms	97.77%	98.22%	97.99%
	Macro-avg	97.79%	97.74%	97.76%

Moreover, the Xception network succeeded the highest average scores, achieving 99.07% F1-Score. Xception is an adaptation from Inception, replacing Inception modules with depth-wise separable convolutions and there are residual connections originally proposed in ResNet [30], placed for all flows. The number of its parameters is quite high too (23 million). Based on the concept of dense connections and features reuse, DenseNet-121 allows better gradient flow using much fewer parameters (8 million). However, its F1-Score exhibited a decrease of 1.31% in contrast to Xception model.

Figure 5: F1-Score plots of (a) Inception-V3, (b) Xception and (c) DenseNet-121 classification model. The x-axis represents the epochs and the y-axis the F1-Score value.

The F1-Score plots for each epoch of the above-mentioned experiments are depicted in Figure 5. According to these plots, Inception-V3 and Xception converged in 12 epochs and DenseNet-121 in 18. The curve's fluctuations occur due to the data shuffling during training.

In order to further evaluate the classification performance of the two-dimensional CNNs, they were tested on an unseen during training dataset as described in Section 3.4. The relevant metrics resulting from this procedure are illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that even on new data, the CNNs can classify correctly the largest part of the drones despite the presence of environmental noise. In particular, Xception and DenseNet-121 succeeded better results than Inception-V3. Nevertheless, Inception's results remain satisfactory, meaning that the model is able to generalize. The choice of the most appropriate model therefore, depends on the nature of the application and its requirements.

Table 2: Precision, recall and F1-Score metrics of the test set for each experiment.

Architecture		Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Inception-V3	Drones	97.61%	86.49%	91.71%
	False Alarms	85.10%	97.33%	90.81%
	Macro-avg	91.36%	91.91%	91.26%
Xception	Drones	96.16%	95.58%	95.87%
	False Alarms	94.47%	95.19%	94.82%
	Macro-avg	95.31%	95.38%	95.35%
DenseNet-121	Drones	93.59%	98.24%	95.86%
	False Alarms	97.64%	91.52%	94.48%
	Macro-avg	95.68%	94.88%	95.17%

5. Conclusion

This work presented a binary classification model approach that uses audio data to detect the existence of a drone. A large dataset was collected from two different environments under real-world conditions and a manual annotation was applied separating them to drones and false alarms. The next steps included the audio recordings pre-processing and the spectrograms extraction via STFT, in order to train two-dimensional CNNs. Utilising data augmentation techniques, three different deep learning architectures were trained, Inception-V3, Xception and Densenet-121 keeping the same optimizer, learning rate and early stopping patience criteria. Their performances were compared and evaluated in terms of precision, recall and F1-Score metrics on a training and test set as well.

The applied experiments showed that all three models achieved high classification scores and are capable of generalizing and detect drones in noisy environments. The Xception model specifically, achieved the highest F1-Score (95.35%) on unseen during training data. Nevertheless, depending on the application's nature, different deep learning models could be implemented. In a real time detection task for example, it is more appropriate to use a model with a small number of parameters (such as DenseNet-121) if the trade-off between number of parameters and classification performance is small. Otherwise, in applications where the accuracy of the model plays the most crucial role, the Xception model would be a better option. In any of those cases, the aforementioned models show great potential for a variety of applications related to critical infrastructure monitoring or public safety and privacy.

Acknowledgments: This work was supported by the EU funded project ALADDIN H2020 under Grant Agreement No. 740859.

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